

Gravimetric Determination of Selenium using N-Benzene-sulphonylhydroxylamine as Reducing Agent

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The method described here allows determination of selenium by reduction of selenious acid in hydrochloric acid using N-benzenesulphonylhydroxylamine. The procedure is particularly useful when selenium has to be determined in presence of tellurium. The method is rapid and simpler than the longer and time-consuming conventional methods and gives results which compare in precision. Analysis of synthetic samples containing selenium and tellurium using the separation method gave acceptable results except in the case of metals which form insoluble chlorides. The proposed procedure is accurate and relatively free from interferences.

A series of hydroxamic acids have been applied for the determination of metal ions. N-Benzoylhydroxylamine has been shown to be a useful reagent for the spectrophotometric and gravimetric determination of several metals¹. There is, however, little quantitative information on the N-benzenesulphonylhydroxylamine as an analytical reagent. Unlike the benzohydroxamic acid, the proposed reagent showed negative tests for iron, copper, but precipitates elementary selenium quantitatively in presence of hydrochloric acid.

The literature on selenium determination contains a number of methods based on the reduction of selenium(IV) and (VI) to elemental selenium. The metal is generally determined as its red variety with reducing agents such as sulphur dioxide², hydroxylamine hydrochloride³, thiourea⁴ and copper(I) chloride⁵. N-Benzenesulphonylhydroxylamine is a very convenient reagent for the gravimetric determination of selenium. The method described here allows rapid determination of selenium in the range of 9.21 to 207.36 mg. It has been applied to the analysis of selenium-tellurium mixtures with a relative standard deviation of less than 0.2%. The reaction can be carried out in the presence of EDTA and tartaric acid which may be used for masking the interfering metals such as copper, bismuth, arsenic and antimony.

Experimental

Selenium solution: In preparing selenium solution, (10mg of Se/ml) an approximate amount of the reagent grade selenious acid (BDH) was dissolved in water and diluted to a litre. The amount of selenium was gravimetrically determined by the hydroxylamine hydrochloride⁶.

Preparation and properties of the reagent: N-Benzene-sulphonylhydroxylamine was prepared by the action of benzenesulphonylchloride on hydroxylamine following the literature procedure⁷. The reagent is a colourless

crystalline compound and is freely soluble in water, alcohol and acetone, m.p. 126°. For use as precipitant, the solution of the reagent, 4 percent (w/v) is generally employed. Hydrochloric acid (BDH. A. R. sp.gr.1.16) was employed for regulation of acidity. For evaluating the extent of interferences, solutions were prepared from reagent grade chemicals to contain known amounts of the ions. Solutions for anion interferences were prepared from sodium salts.

General procedure: An aliquot of a standard selenium solution was transferred to 400 ml pyrex beaker. About 40 ml of hydrochloric acid followed by 25 ml of reagent solution were added and the solution was brought to total volume of 100 ml. Reduction of selenious acid to black elemental selenium was carried out on a water bath. The precipitate was immediately filtered off on a sintered glass filter (porosity 4), washed with hot water, alcohol and after drying at 110° was weighed. The results obtained are shown in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

For getting the optimum conditions of the complete reduction, preliminary experiments were carried out. Effects of acidity and time on precipitation was studied in detail. To an aliquot of selenium, varying amounts of hydrochloric acid were added. The study disclosed that the precipitation of selenium is complete from little above 3.0 to about 7.0N hydrochloric acid, approximately 30-70 percent by volume. The results are given in Table 1. It was decided to use 40 ml of the acid in the total volume of 100 ml. The reagent was added in the form of a 4 percent solution in water and 1 ml of the solution is usually sufficient for the precipitation of 5 mg of the metal.

Recovery of seleniums: Solutions containing varying amount of selenium were treated by general procedure. Satisfactory results were obtained for as little as 9.21 mg of selenium with an overall recovery of 99.8 to 100.2%.

(Table 2). Under the conditions employed in these studies, no volatilisation of selenium was evidenced at any time. The procedure involved may be considered as perfectly safe.

TABLE 1—CONDITIONS FOR DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM

Se taken mg	HCl N	Time allowed for pptn h	Se found mg	Recovery %
46.08	2.5	8.0	45.98	99.8
92.16	3.0	2.0	92.32	100.2
92.16	3.5	1.5	92.08	99.9
92.16	4.0	1.0	92.10	99.9
46.08	5.0	1.0	46.01	99.8
46.08	6.0	1.0	45.98	99.8
69.12	7.0	1.0	69.06	99.7

Interference study : A number of cations and anions were tested for a possible interference effect on the method. The effect of these ions is illustrated in Table 3 which refers to a final acidity of 4.0*N* hydrochloric acid and 1.0 g reagent. At this acidity, interferences from bismuth, arsenic and antimony were masked with tartaric acid. Selenium may be completely separated from copper using EDTA as a masking agent for copper, which, however, does not form a complex with selenite ion. When the metals which form insoluble chlorides are present, the results will be high. Among the anions nitrate, sulphate, phosphate, tartrate, acetate did not interfere.

TABLE 2—RECOVERY OF SELENIUM (HCl, 4*N*)

Se taken mg	Se obtained mg	Recovery %
9.21	9.20	99.9
11.52	11.49	99.8
18.43	18.40	99.9
23.04	23.01	99.9
46.08	46.04	99.9
69.12	69.19	100.1
92.16	92.10	99.9
115.20	115.32	100.1
138.24	138.10	99.9
184.32	183.96	99.8
200.44	200.84	100.2
207.36	207.15	99.9

Determination of selenium and tellurium in an admixture : Synthetic solutions containing definite amounts of selenium (46.08 mg) and tellurium (61.04 mg) were treated by the general procedure using hydrochloric acid. Selenium was completely precipitated in about an hour (Table 4). Good agreement was obtained between the results from the proposed method and those from conventional methods⁸. The procedure is therefore considered suitable for the analysis of selenium-tellurium mixtures.

TABLE 3—INTERFERENCES IN DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM (92.16 MG) WITH *N*-BENZENESULPHONYLHYDROXYLAMINE (HCl, 4*N*).

Diverse ion	Amount added mg	Se obtained mg	Recovery %
Cu (II)*	200	92.04	99.9
Ni (II)	100	92.08	99.9
Mg (II)	60	92.10	99.9
Mn (II)	60	92.35	100.2
Zn (II)	100	92.25	100.1
Bi (III) †	50	92.10	99.9
As (III) †	50	92.03	99.8
Sb (III) †	60	92.04	99.9
Cd (II)	100	92.33	100.1
Co (II)	100	92.10	99.9
Tartaric acid	1000	92.15	100.0
EDTA	500	92.33	100.1
Nitrate	1000	92.12	100.0
Sulphate	1000	92.33	100.1

* Masked with EDTA ; † Masked with tartaric acid

Determination of tellurium in the filtrate : Tellurium in the filtrate was determined using thiourea. The filtrate was neutralised by ammonia and heated to about 70° on a water bath. To this a solution containing 3 g of thiourea was added. Heating was continued till tellurium completely settled. This requires not more than 1h. The precipitate was collected, washed and dried. Recovery of tellurium was quantitative in every case (Table 4).

TABLE 4—SELENIUM-TELLURIUM ANALYSIS ON SYNTHETIC SAMPLES (HCl, 4*N*).

Se taken mg	Te added mg	Se found mg	σ	Te found mg	σ
		46.02		61.16	
		46.07		60.92	
46.08	61.04	46.04	0.07	61.08	0.1
		46.14		60.88	
		45.94		60.94	

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